

5. A. MORAIT and A. MAVRODIN, *Farmacia*, 1980, **28**, 229 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1981, **95**, 6943).
 6. N. SRIVASTAVA, S. BAHADUR, H. N. VERMA and M. M. A. A. KHAN, *Curr. Sci.*, 1951, **28**, 344.
 7. M. GIANTURCO and A. RONEO, *Gazz. Chem. Ital.*, 1953, **82**, 429 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1954, **48**, 2074).

One-pot Conversion of 2-Methyl-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one into 3-Substituted-2-styrylquinazolin-4-ones

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QUINAZOLIN-4-ones are important class of compounds and their chemistry continues to be of considerable interest¹⁻³. In connection with our studies in heterocycles carrying an activated methyl group, the title reaction was investigated. The synthesis of **5** is usually carried out in a stepwise fashion¹, but in the present method, all the steps were carried out in the same flask (see Experimental). Products were characterised by ¹H nmr data, which ruled out the alternative structure **6**, and these were confirmed by comparison with authentic samples. The relevant physical constants are given in Table 1. The amides (**3**), which are the precursors of **4**, however, could not be isolated.

dryness under reduced pressure and the resulting compound (**2**) was treated with a primary amine (1.1 mol) and glacial acetic acid (10 ml/g of **1**). An aromatic aldehyde (1.1 mol) was then added to the mixture and refluxed for ~2.5 h using freshly fused sodium acetate as a catalyst. It was concentrated to dryness over a steam-bath and the crude product

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 3-SUBSTITUTED-2-STYRYLQUINAZOLIN-4-ONES (**5**)

Compd. no.	R	Ar	Yield ^a %	M.p. ^{**} °C	δ (ppm) (CDCl ₃ /TMS)
5a	Ph	Ph	60	198 ^a	6.25 (1H, d, J 15.4 Hz, PhOH=CH), 7.09–7.68 (12H, m, Ar-H), 7.81 (1H, d, J 15.4 Hz, PhCH=CH), 8.18 (2H, d, Ar-H)
5b	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	Ph	61	201 ^b	6.28 (1H, d, J 15.4 Hz, PhOH=OH), 7.06–7.72 (11H, m, Ar-H), 7.97 (1H, d, J 15.4 Hz, PhCH=CH), 8.18 (2H, d, Ar-H)
5c	4-MeO-C ₆ H ₄	Ph	60	220 ^a	3.88 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 6.46 (1H, d, J 16.4 Hz, PhOH=CH), 7.00–7.83 (11H, m, Ar-H), 7.88 (1H, d, J 16.4 Hz, PhCH=CH), 8.30 (2H, d, Ar-H)
5d	4-HOOC-C ₆ H ₄	Ph	59	285 ^c	Insufficiently soluble
5e	Ph	2-HO-C ₆ H ₄	47	269 ^a	Insufficiently soluble
5f	2-HOOC-C ₆ H ₄	3,4-MeO, HO-C ₆ H ₄	45	205 ^c	Insufficiently soluble

^aBased on *N*-acetylanthranilic acid taken. ^{**}Lit. reference ^aRef. 4, ^bRef. 5, ^cRef. 2.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The ¹H nmr spectra were recorded on a JEOL 90Q spectrophotometer.

3-Substituted 2-styrylquinazolin-4-ones (5); General procedure: To a suspension of *N*-acetylanthranilic acid (**1**; 1.0 mol) in dry benzene (25 ml/g of the acid) containing triethylamine (2.2 mol), tosylchloride (1.01 mol) was added and the mixture shaken for a few min at room temperature. Triethylamine salts were filtered off and washed with dry benzene. The filtrate was concentrated to

was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol to give a pure compound. The physical data are given in Table 1.

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References

- 1 W. L. F. ARMAREGO in "Fused Pyrimidines: Quinazolines", ed D. J. BROWN, Part 1, Interscience, New York, 1967, p. 107.

2. R. SOLIMAN and F. S. G. SOLIMAN, *Synthesis*, 1979, 808.
3. R. W. LEIBY, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1985, 50, 2926.
4. M. T. BOGERT and G. D. BEAL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 34, 516.
5. A. SAMMOUR, M. I. B. SELIM and M. A. ABDO, *UAR J. Chem.*, 1971, 14, 197 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1972, 77, 114852).

Chemical Examination of Fruits and Leaves of *Peucedanum grande*

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PEUCEDANUM grande an aromatic umbellifer is reported¹ to be used in the indigenous system of medicine as carminative, stimulant and diuretic. Osthol, byakangelicin and imperatorin have been isolated from its roots^{2,3}, while columbianadin, phellopterin and byakangelicol have been additionally reported in fruits^{4,5}. The present work concerns with the isolation of a few more coumarins from the leaves and fruits as well a report on the composition of the essential oil from the fruits.

Isolation of coumarins from leaves :

Air-dried powder (850 g) of the leaves of *P. grande* was extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) in a Soxhlet apparatus to obtain a dark green oil (44.5 g), a part (20 g) of which was chromatographed over silica gel (600 g). Elution with benzene gave a white solid which was crystallised as prismatic needles (1.7 g, m.p. 83–84°) from benzene–petroleum ether mixture, and characterised as osthol by comparison of its uv⁶, pmr⁷ and mass⁸ spectra, $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 720 (C=O) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=C). Further elution with benzene yielded another solid which was purified by washing repeatedly with petroleum ether followed by crystallisation from benzene. The white needles (20 mg), m.p. 184–86°, could be identified as bergapten from uv⁶ and pmr⁷ spectra; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 720, 1 600 and 1 578 cm⁻¹; *m/e* 216 (*M*⁺), 201 (*M*⁺–CH₃), 188 (*M*⁺–CO) and 173 (*M*⁺–(CO+CH₃)).

Elution with benzene–ethyl acetate (19 : 1) gave yellow needles (120 mg), m.p. 149–51°, upon crystallisation from ethyl acetate–benzene; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 710, 1 600 and 1 590 cm⁻¹. The compound was characterised as isopimpinellin from its uv⁶, pmr⁷ and mass¹⁰ spectra.

Elution with benzene–ethyl acetate (9 : 1) afforded small quantity of a compound (10 mg), m.p. 107–09°; $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) 221, 248 and 300 nm; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 700, 1 620 and 1 580 cm⁻¹. The pmr spectra of the compound was in full agreement with

that of heraclenin⁷. The gummy mass obtained from benzene–ethyl acetate (4 : 1) fractions was treated with hot benzene to give a solid and crystallised as needles (110 mg), m.p. 163–67° by slow evaporation of its chloroform solution at room temperature; $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) 212, 218, 250, 263 and 325 nm; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 480 (OH), 1 700 and 1 600 cm⁻¹. It was identified as columbianetin by comparison of its pmr⁷ and mass¹¹ spectra.

Isolation of coumarins from fruits :

The fruits (1.0 kg) purchased from local market were powdered and extracted successively with petroleum ether, chloroform and methanol in a Soxhlet apparatus. The petroleum ether extract, a dark yellowish green oil (67 g), deposited a yellow solid (8.0 g) which was chromatographed over silica gel (250 g). Elution with benzene gave bergapten (0.75 g). Elution with benzene–ethyl acetate (9 : 1) afforded a yellow solid (40 mg), m.p. 226–30° which was characterised as alloimperatorin on the basis of its mass spectrum¹²; $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) 226, 242, 252, 268 and 315 nm; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 320 (OH), 1 720 and 1 590 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 6.3 (1H, d, *J* 9.5 Hz, H–3), 8.1 (1H, d, *J* 9.5 Hz, H–4), 6.85 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, H–3'), 7.7 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, H–2'), 5.2 (1H, t, CH olefinic), 3.7 (2H, d, CH₂–benzylic), 1.83 (3H, s) and 1.67 (3H, s, allylic methyls) and 2.74 (br, D₂O exchangeable OH). Further elution with benzene–ethyl acetate (9 : 1) gave another yellow compound which crystallised as needles from methanol (180 mg), m.p. 209–12°, and was characterised as 5-methoxy-8-hydroxypsoralen; $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) 226, 276 and 316 nm¹³; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 340–20, 1 700, 1 600 and 1 585 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 6.3 (1H, d, *J* 9.5 Hz, H–3), 8.1 (1H, d, *J* 9.5 Hz, H–4), 6.98 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, H–3), 7.65 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, H–2), 4.12 (3H, s, OCH₃) and 2.78 (br s, D₂O exchangeable OH); *m/e* 232 (*M*⁺), 217 (*M*⁺–CH₃), 201 (*M*⁺–OCH₃) and 189 (*M*⁺–(CO+CH₃)). No change in the chemical shifts of H–4 proton after acetylation confirmed the position of OH group at C–8. Elution with benzene–ethyl acetate (4 : 1 to 1 : 1) gave byakangelicin (1.95 g), m.p. 124–26°, which was identified on the basis of the reported data^{4,14}.

The oil remaining after removal of the solid deposit was steam-distilled and the residue (20 g) was chromatographed over silica gel (600 g). It led to the isolation of bergapten (100 mg, benzene fractions) and byakangelicin (400 mg, benzene–ethyl acetate 4 : 1 to 1 : 1 fractions).

Elution with petroleum ether–benzene (1 : 1) gave an oil containing uv fluorescent substances. Since attempts to separate any solid failed, the oil was saponified. The unsaponifiable matter (2.9 g) was chromatographed over silica gel (100 g) to yield osthol (55 mg from benzene fractions) and columbianetin (130 g from benzene–ethyl acetate 9 : 1 fraction). Tlc studies indicated the formation of columbianetin during saponification by hydrolysis of columbianadin which has already been reported⁴ in fruits.